

Relationship between Anabolic Steroids and Left Ventricular Hypertrophy Disease in Simplified General Idea for Non-Specialized Readers

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ABSTRACT

The goal of this article is, to compare between cardiovascular system condition in normal body and on anabolic steroids users like bodybuilders in general simple idea according to past researches experiments in simplified way for non-specialized industry readers.

Keywords: Steroids, Anabolic, bodybuilders, bodybuilding, cardiovascular.

INTRODUCTION

Anabolic steroids started to appear in the world on 1950s .Since that time, lot of people specially those who want to gain a big bulk of muscles in short time started abusing its usage and it included side effects like: hypogonadism, testicular atrophy, impaired spermatogenesis, gynaecomastia and some psychiatric disorders. Those signs were the most common cases at that time. But, does it really affect on Cardiovascular system?

Simply YES. One of the most common cardiac diseases for anabolic steroids users is left ventricular hypertrophy. Myocardium of left ventricle gets so much bigger than myocardium of normal healthy adult.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

in the Framingham Heart Study who were 40 years of age or older and free of clinically apparent cardiovascular disease, in whom left ventricular mass was determined echocardiographically. During a four-year follow-up period, there were 208 incident cardiovascular events, 37 deaths from cardiovascular disease, and 124 deaths from all causes. Left ventricular mass, determined echocardiographically, was associated with all outcome events. This relation persisted after we adjusted for age, diastolic blood pressure, pulse pressure, treatment for hypertension, cigarette smoking, diabetes, obesity, the ratio of total cholesterol to high-density lipoprotein cholesterol, and electrocardiographic evidence of left ventricular hypertrophy. In men, the risk factor-adjusted relative risk of cardiovascular disease was 1.49 for each increment of 50 g per meter in left ventricular mass corrected for the subject's height (95 percent confidence interval, 1.20 to 1.85); in women, it was 1.57 (95 percent confidence interval, 1.20 to 2.04). Left ventricular mass (corrected for height) was also associated with the incidence of death from cardiovascular disease (relative risk, 1.73 [95 percent confidence interval, 1.19 to 2.52] in men and 2.12 [95 percent confidence interval, 1.28 to 3.49] in women). The majority of that is because anabolic steroids has indirect effect with the factors which are mentioned above which is direct proportional with cardiac disorders.

CONCLUSION

Anabolic steroids have very effective side effects on heart compared to normal athletics heart.

REFERENCES

- Cardiac effects of anabolic steroids, introduction <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1768197/>
- Levy D, Garrison R, Savage D, et al. Prognostic implications of echocardiographically determined left ventricular mass in the Framingham heart study. *N Engl J Med* 1990; 322: 1561–6.
- Fallo F, Budano S, Sonino N, et al. Left ventricular structural characteristics in Cushing’s syndrome. *J Hum Hypertens* 1994; 8: 509–13.
- Delles C, Schmidt BM, Muller HJ, et al. Functional relevance of aldosterone for the determination of left ventricular mass. *Am J Cardiol* 2003; 91: 297–301.